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A STUDY OF PATTERN OF REFERRALS IN LIAISON PSYCHIATRY

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ABSTRACT

Liaison psychiatry specializes in bridging psychiatric services to other specialities. It has been actively intervening in the reduction of the communication gap between the various specialities in many health care setups. Thereby it provides them the ability to acquire adequate understanding about the intricacies involved in treating patients with physical and psychiatric co-morbidities. Efficient communication between different levels of care has a great impact on quality of health care. Objectives: To assess the source of referral, reason for referral, the psychiatric diagnosis of the patients referred and the Psychiatric treatment initiated by the referring team and the knowledge of the illness. Materials and method: The study was a cross sectional study conducted on the out patients and inpatients referred to the psychiatric department in a tertiary care hospital in central India. It was completed in the time period of 3 months from June 1st 2014 to August 15th 2014 with a sample size of 150 patients. All the referred patients were evaluated by a consultant psychiatrist and diagnosis was made according to the diagnostic guidelines of ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases -10th Edition). Results: Out of the total number of patients who were referred 79(52.6%) patients were males and 71(47.3%) were females. The mean age of the study population was 36.01 years. A majority of the patients belonged to the age group of 21-30 years. A majority of the referrals were made from the department of medicine (n=76, 50.6%). The various reasons for psychiatric referral were analyzed and it was found that the most common reason was the presence abnormal behaviour (n=37, 24.6%). The most common psychiatric diagnosis made was substance use disorders (n=51, 34%) Conclusion: The observations of our study clearly show that there is significant gap existing in consultation liaison psychiatry as reflected in the profile and patterns referrals assessed. Early diagnosis and management of psychiatric disorders in patients presenting to the other departments with various physical illnesses definitely hasten recovery, reduce morbidity and improve quality of life. The way ahead is too long in this field and the need for improving the liaison is crucial in reducing the burden of morbidity and improving the quality of life of the patient and their carers.

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INTRODUCTION

Liaison psychiatry specializes in bridging psychiatric services to other specialities. It has been actively intervening in the reduction of the communication gap between the various specialities in many health care setups. Thereby it provides them the ability to acquire adequate understanding about the intricacies involved in treating patients with physical and psychiatric co-morbidities. Efficient communication between different levels of care has a great impact on quality of health care. Therefore, consultation liaison psychiatric services can be considered as a key player between psychiatry and the other medical specialties.^[1]

History shows that general hospitals have had an illustrious role in the evolution of psychiatry. They have provided a fertile land for the development of inpatient psychiatric units, consultation-liaison psychiatry, psychosomatic medicine, med-psych units, outpatient psychiatric clinics, emergency psychiatric care and a whole spectrum of resources for the communities in which they live.^[2]

Prior to 1930, mental health services in this country were confined to the mental hospitals. The C-L (consultation-liaison) Psychiatry as a subspecialty started in 1930s with the institution of general hospital psychiatric units (GHPUs). The pioneers of the first GHPU in 1933 were Dr Girindra Shekhar at R. G. Kar Medical College and Hospital, Calcutta.^[3]

Research in the field of Consultation Liaison psychiatry is gradually gaining momentum considering the importance of this area. There is very high prevalence of depressive and other disorders in developing nations and only a tiny proportion receives psychiatric care or treatment. In most countries the principal source of help is primary care physicians. The World Health Organization researches done in various countries confirmed that depressive, anxiety, neurasthenic and substance misuse disorders are the most common disorders seen in this setting. These psychiatric morbidities are often closely associated with the presence of physical illness that can have a profound bearing on the occupational functioning of persons suffering from such illnesses.^[4] The primary medical illness itself can have a prolonged course and worse outcome when adequate attention is not given to an early detection and management of psychiatric co morbidities

Inadequate training in psychiatry at undergraduate level is to a large extent responsible for quite a number of missed diagnoses of psychiatric problems in medical /surgical patients. Until now, formal consultation liaison (C-L) psychiatric units are almost absent in India. For future planning of psychiatric and C - L psychiatric services in general hospitals, it is important to know the degree of awareness of clinicians in different specialities about the psychiatric disorders in their patients. It is equally important to assess their attitude towards psychiatry and psychiatric referral, the types and pattern of referrals, their expectations from the psychiatrist and their opinion about utility of the psychiatrist in general hospital settings.^[5]

With this need in mind we conducted a study to assess the profile and pattern of referrals in Liaison Psychiatry in a rural general hospital set up. Since it was a medical college there were all medical and surgical departments available in the same campus and consultation liaison have been part and parcel of its functioning from many years. The aim of this study was to assess the profile and pattern of referred patients from various departments for Psychiatric evaluation and management. The objectives were to assess the source of referral, reason for referral, the psychiatric diagnosis of the patients, psychiatric treatment initiated by the referring team based on their knowledge of the illness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a cross sectional study conducted on the out patients and inpatients referred to the psychiatric department in a tertiary care hospital in central India which was completed in the time period of 3 months from 1st June 2014 to 15th August 2014 with a sample size of 150. It was carried out after obtaining an ethical clearance from the hospital ethical committee.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria:

- 1) All referrals from Departments seeking psychiatric evaluation. 2) Referred patients who were willing to give written informed consent.
- 2) Patients who did not give informed consent or those who could not co-operate due to impairing medical debilities or cognitive impairments were excluded from the study.

All the referred patients were evaluated by a consultant psychiatrist and diagnosis was made according to the diagnostic guidelines, as per ICD-10 (International Statistical Classification of Diseases) – Classification of Mental and Behavioural Disorders.⁽⁶⁾ Other details like socio-demographic profile, source of referral and reason for referral and medication prescribed along with their dosages were recorded in a semi structured proforma. The data was analysed using SPSS version 16 software using appropriate statistical tools.

RESULTS

A total of 150 patients were referred for psychiatric consultation from various departments during the study period. Out of the total number of patients who were referred 79(52.6%) patients were males and 71(47.3%) were females. The mean age of the study population was 36.01 years. A majority of the patients belonged to the age group of 21-30 years. The number of patients in the age groups of 10-20 years and above 60 years were 6 (4%) and 5 (3%) respectively. (Table 1).

Table 1: Age wise and gender wise distribution of patients

Age Group(yrs)	Male	Female	Total
10-20	4	2	6
21-30	26	35	61
31-40	36	23	59
41-50	6	5	11
51-60	3	5	8
>60	4	1	5
Total	79	71	150
Mean Age	36.5	35.8	36.01

Majority of the referrals were made from the department of medicine (n=76, 50.6%). Other major sources of psychiatric referrals were departments of surgery (n=28, 18.6%) and orthopaedics (n=29, 19.3%). A smaller amount of referral were found to be there from other departments like Paediatrics, OBG (Obstetrics and Gynaecology)and Dermatology (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to Department of Referral.

Referral Dept	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Medicine	76	50.6
OBG	3	2
Ortho	29	19.3
Pediatrics	5	3.3
Surgery	28	18.6
Dermatology	2	1.3
Chest Medicine	4	2.6
Cardiology	2	1.3
ENT	1	0.6
Total	150	100

The various reasons for psychiatric referral were analyzed and it was found that the most common reason for referring for psychiatry consultation was presence abnormal behaviour (n=37, 24.6%) most often a part of delirium. Substance use (n=36, 24%) and insomnia (n=20, 13.3%) were the other major reasons for referral. Vague somatic complaints and self harm attempts also were significant part of referrals. Some referrals were for psychiatric fitness before surgeries, renal transplantation etc and few were for IQ assessment and Specific Learning disability. Patients with a previous psychiatric history were also referred although currently they had no psychiatric symptoms (Table 3)

Table 3: Distribution of Patients According to Reason for Referral.

Reason	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Abnormal Behavior	37	24.6
Alcohol Use	36	24
Decreased Sleep	20	13.3
Depressive Symptoms	6	4
Fitness	6	4
IQ Assessment	6	4
Somatic complaints	14	9.3
Benzodiazepine dependence	1	0.6
Previous psychiatric disorder	8	5.3
Attempted Self harm	11	7.3
Learning disability	1	0.6
Seizure disorder	2	1.3
Anxiety Related to Procedures	2	1.3
Total	150	100

The most frequent psychiatric diagnosis made were alcohol dependence disorders (n=51, 34%) and Delirium (n=38, 25%). 13(8.6%) were found to have depressive disorder the call for which were frequented made as insomnia or somatisation symptoms. No psychiatric diagnosis was made in 2.6% (n=4) of the patients. (Table4)

Table 4: Diagnosis According to ICD 10.

Diagnosis	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Depressive Disorder	13	8.6
Alcohol Dependence	51	34
Acute and transient psychotic disorder	2	1.3
Somatization Disorder	12	8
Mental Retardation	8	5.3
Delirium	38	25
Delusional Disorder	2	1.3
Schizophrenia	4	2.6
Bipolar Affective Disorder	2	1.3
BZD dependence	2	1.3
Post Encephalitic Sequel	1	0.6
Seizures	1	0.6
Deliberate Self Harm	4	2.6
Primary insomnia	2	1.3
Sexual dysfunction	2	1.3
Anxiety disorder	2	1.3
Nil Diagnosis	4	2.6
Total	150	100

In the study population frequently prescribed medication was Benzodiazepines in 48(28%) patients. Patients were also receiving antipsychotics and antidepressants some of them prescribed by previous treating doctors.(Table 5).A significant number of patients were getting only multi vitamin -45(30%) although they were acutely symptomatic.

Table 5: Distribution of Patients According to Medication Prescribed

Medication Prescribed	No of patients	Percentage (%)
Antipsychotic	31	20.6
Antidepressants	20	13.3
Benzodiazepines	42	28
Multivitamin	45	30
Nil Intervention	11	7.3
Mood stabilizer (Lithium, Sodium Valproate)	1	0.6
Total	150	100

DISCUSSION

Age distribution showed that most of the patients (40.6%) belonged to the age group of 21-30 years. Similar results were seen in the studies done on referred patients by Aghanwaet al and Bhogale et al [7,8]. It was also noted that a minority of patients were above 60 years. A significant reason for such few number of elderly in our study could be probably because detecting psychiatric symptoms in an elderly person is often difficult as they mimic clinical presentations of medical illnesses per se. Very often these presentations are taken as an invariable part of growing old or the co morbid illness associated. This may be also attributed to the fact that in rural areas especially with a low socio economic background, care of the geriatric age group is largely being neglected or does not become a priority as there is a lack of awareness of the mental health issues affecting the elderly persons. Persons in this age group often do not come out with such symptoms or do not seek help. In our experience, elderly get referred for a psychiatric consultation only when the behavioural issues associated become distressing or difficult to manage. The number of males (57%) outnumbered females in our study which was a finding similar to the study done by Aktharjaved et al. [9]

It was found that the most common psychiatric diagnosis made was substance abuse disorders, commonest among them being alcohol dependence. It may be worth mentioning here that despite being a dry district, the use of substances is highly rampant in this region, more so the use of illegal substances. This often leads to multiple physical and psychiatric complications in the users frequently ending them up in medical or surgical wards. Our finding on substance use was similar to the findings of Singh et al [10] which showed that 14.5% of the referrals were for substance use disorders. The above findings reveal the dire need of addressing substance abuse problems in persons seeking medical help in a general hospital.

The most common diagnosis followed by substance use disorders was that of delirium (24.6%). 7.5 per cent of the patients were referred for risk assessment and management of deliberate self harm which correlates with the study of Bhogale et al, Chency et al and Aghanawa et al [7,8,11] in which cases of self harm were high. The higher prevalence of self harm can be attributed to the fact that majority of our population belonged to younger age group in which DSH is found to be consistently high. It has to be also noted that the study conducted in an area where majority of people engage in farming and depend on the yearly crops for their sustenance. It is worth mentioning here that this area has a high incidence of farmer's suicide although it was not clear from our study if stress related to farming was the reason for DSH.

Majority of psychiatric referrals were from the department of medicine (76%) for abnormal behaviour most of them turning out to be delirium (24.6%). This was followed by alcohol dependence (24%) and insomnia (20%). This correlates with the study done by Narayana Keerthi et al and Bhoghale G.S et al ^[6,8] which reported that 59% of their patients were referred from the department of medicine with almost similar distribution of diagnosis.

Benzodiazepines (Clonazepam, Lorazepam, Chlordiazepoxide) were the most commonly prescribed medication (28%) among all the psychotropic medicines prescribed by other medical and surgical departments. Although a number of referred patients were on antipsychotics (20.6%) (Olanzapine, Risperidon, Haloperidol, Quitipine) and antidepressants (Amitriptyline, Prothiaden, Escitalopram, Sertraline) (13.3%) the prescribed doses were not adequate for a good therapeutic effect and were started randomly without necessary psychiatric evaluation of the patient.

It is a common practice to prescribe benzodiazepines frequently as add on therapy whenever the symptoms of anxiety or insomnia are encountered in the medical and surgical wards. Often these prescriptions are under dosed and unchecked resulting in patients increasing and continuing the dose without further consultations.

It was observed during the study that a number of patients were referred without any clear psychiatric symptoms or diagnosis. On the other hand some patients who needed real psychiatric intervention were referred after a huge time lag resulting in the refusal of psychiatric transfer over by the patients and caretakers for further management. A few occasions it was also revealed that the patients were not informed about the referrals causing distress and initial non-cooperation. On a few occasions it was also observed that the previously advised treatment is not appropriately carried out or further liaison delayed resulting in a delay in showing the desired improvement.

The basic awareness of symptoms and diagnosis of psychiatric illnesses is found to be lacking from evaluation of referral pattern. It is often noticed that any mention of a psychiatric symptom rings an alarm more so when dealing with the patients in emergency care units or initial evaluation of patients in other medico-surgical wards. Such precautionary calls increase the burden on the treating team of psychiatrist. There is a need to encourage multi-disciplinary interaction in the care of patients who come to the general hospital settings seeking health care. It is vital for an early identification and management of psychiatric morbidities highly prevalent with other medical illnesses. This is equally important in the management of the medical illnesses they are presenting with as both have a direct relationship. The relation of psychiatry with other medical illnesses has progressed from the times and phases of psychodynamic understanding of medical symptoms, sub syndromal symptoms of various primary psychiatric disorders to diagnosing syndromal psychiatric disorders.

Over the years, the number of GHPU's have increased significantly ^[2] thus resulting in a greater interaction among psychiatrists, physicians and other specialists ⁽¹²⁾ It is also important to reduce the communication gap between the treating team and the psychiatry team. Interdisciplinary meetings, Postgraduate and undergraduate teaching activities, projects and the periodic presentations and classes will be some of the measures which can boost the communication and enhance knowledge in this regard. The necessity of such activities to be of a give and take nature is implied in a liaison set up for continued cooperation and continuity at the interdepartmental level.

Consultation –Liaison needs to be given more importance in the post graduate curriculum as well especially when the clinical postings are decided to allied medical branches. This will help the physicians, surgeons and other medical specialists to identify the psychiatric symptoms in time and refer for a psychiatric evaluation and management without unnecessarily groping in the dark. This will also help reducing the unnecessary time lag towards cure. There is also a need to cut down the over prescription of benzodiazepines as these are found to be the most commonly overused group of medication in our study.

CONCLUSION

The observations of our study clearly show a significant gap in the area of consultation liaison psychiatry as seen in symptom identification, referral patterns and the medication usage. Early diagnosis and management of psychiatric disorders in patients presenting to the other departments with various presentations of physical illnesses definitely hasten recovery and reduce morbidity. A timely psychiatric intervention can reduce the period of hospital stay and thereby the burden to the patient as well as their family members. It can make a huge impact in the cost effectiveness of medical care in areas which is mostly illiterate and economically backward and struggle for meeting the basic needs. It can also help preventing many chronic psychiatric morbidities going undetected and unattended and to promote wellbeing of the persons attending our hospitals. Our study shows that the way ahead is too long in this field and the need for improving the liaison is crucial in reducing the burden of morbidity and improving the quality of life of the patient and their care givers. There is an urgent need to improve the liaison between psychiatry and other medical branches in order to achieve the desired outcome with regard to management of various morbidities and reducing the burden of care.

This current research was limited by time and less number of referrals. The study did not include other objective assessment of parameters like awareness of the treating team,

Recommended Future Research

We should aim at further improving and increasing research in this area including more patients and for a longer period of time. Qualitative assessment of the awareness of medical students and practitioners regarding need for and time of psychiatric referrals can be helpful to improve Liaison services in the future. Conducting interdisciplinary projects and programmes aimed at improving the knowledge and awareness in this area can also be helpful. As early intervention and timely management of psychiatric illnesses can enhance the quality of life of the patients, a collaborative approach can enhance the comprehensive quality care of mentally ill patients.

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REFERENCES

1. Ajagallay RK, Das S, Salankar H, Chanchlani R. A clinical audit of referrals to the psychiatry department from other specialties: a study from central India. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences* 2014; 3(13): 3401-7.
2. Lipsitt DR. Psychiatry and the general hospital in an age of uncertainty. *World Psychiatry* 2003; 2(2):87-92.
3. Grover S. State of Consultation-Liaison Psychiatry in India: Current status and vision for future. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry* 2011; 53(3):202-13.
4. Creed F. Consultation-liaison psychiatry worldwide. *World Psychiatry* 2003;2(2):93-4.
5. Chadda RK, Shome S. Psychiatric aspects of clinical practice in general hospitals: a survey of non-psychiatric clinicians. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry* 1996; 38(2):86-92.
6. World Health Organization. The ICD 10 classification of mental and behavioural disorders: Diagnostic criteria for research. Geneva, World Health Organization;1993
7. Aghanwa H. Consultation Liaison Psychiatry in Fiji. *Pacific Health Dialogue*. 2002;9
8. Bhogale GS, Katta RM, Heble SP, Sinha UK, Patil BA. Psychiatric referrals in multi speciality hospital. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 2000;42(2):188-94.
9. Akhtar J, Farooq S, Ali A. Psychiatric Referrals in a multidisciplinary hospital. *JPML*.4.
10. Singh PM, Vaidya L, Shrestha DM, Tajhya R, Shakya S. Consultation liaison psychiatry at Nepal Medical College and Teaching Hospital. *Nepal Med Coll J*. 2009; 11(4):272-74.
11. Chen CY, Yeh SS. The present state psychiatric consultation in Change Gung Memorial Hospital, Keelung: a report of clinical characteristics. *Change-Keng Hsueh*.1996; 19(4):331-36.
12. Sarada MM. Mental Health in Independent India: The Early Years. In: Agarwal SP, editor. *Mental Health and Indian Prospective*; New Delhi: Directorate General of Health Sciences Ministry of Health and Family Welfare; 2005; 30-36.

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